

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

PHENOMENOLOGY AND SEMIOTICS OF THE ARTISTIC IMAGE IN REALIST PAINTING: EXPERIENCE, BELIEF, AND INTERPRETATION

Skovronskyi B.

*PhD in Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor
Department of Design and Fine Arts*

*Mykhailo Drahomanov Ukrainian State University
Kyiv, Ukraine*

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5413-6630>

ABSTRACT

This article examines the artistic image in realist painting at the intersection of phenomenological and semiotic methodologies as a phenomenon formed by human consciousness. Its starting thesis is that the image can be reduced neither to the reproduction of the external features of an object nor to its simple sign substitution; rather, it emerges as a special form of conditional yet convincing reality constituted in consciousness through depiction. In this regard, the central problem of the article is to clarify how a real thing is transformed into an artistic image, which factors ensure this transformation, and what mode such a transformation of content assumes.

The article analyzes the state of scholarly development of the topic in phenomenology, aesthetics, semiotics, and art theory. Special attention is given to the concepts of Husserl, Ingarden, Merleau-Ponty, Losev, and Deely. It is shown that phenomenology makes it possible to describe the image as an intentional object of consciousness, whereas semiotics reveals the mechanisms of its functioning as a sign-mediated form of experience. Particular importance in the study is given to the concepts of belief, experience, presentation, interpretation, and interpretant, through which the mechanism of the emergence of figurative reality is specified.

The article also considers the relationship between phenomenological and semiotic approaches and shows that they do not exclude but rather complement one another in the analysis of the pictorial image. Using examples from well-known works of painting, especially those of Cezanne, it demonstrates that realist painting not only reproduces an object but also forms a special mode of its presence in which the depicted becomes self-sufficient both aesthetically and semantically.

In conclusion, it is argued that the artistic image in realist painting is an intentionally and sign-mediated form of aesthetic reality that arises in the process of correlation between experience and belief, carried out through interpretation and the presentation of the image.

Keywords: artistic image, depiction, realism, painting, phenomenology, semiotics, intentionality, interpretant, presentation, aesthetic perception.

Introduction. The concept of the image belongs to the basic categories of philosophy, aesthetics, psychology, and art studies. In the traditional sense, the image is associated with the reflection of reality in human consciousness, with the formation of an idea of an object, phenomenon, or event, and with the transmission of content through a sensuously expressive form. In this meaning, the image may be interpreted as a "subjective picture of the world," a "sign system," or a "universal carrier of information." At the same time, contemporary culture, marked by multimedia, interartistic synthesis, clip thinking, and complex regimes of visual communication, actualizes the need for a broader, meta-artistic understanding of the image.

Realist painting requires particular attention in this context. Despite the obvious historical stability of this form of art, it is precisely here that the problem of the relationship between depiction and reality, sign and object, the visible and the thinkable, the given and the experienced arises most acutely. Realist depiction reveals a paradoxical nature: it is created from lines, patches of color, and relations of light and shade, that is, from elements that in fact have no commonality with the depicted object, yet at the same time are perceived as its presence. It is precisely this capacity to replace a real thing with its figurative reality that provides grounds

for a deeper analysis of the artistic image as a specific mode of being.

In this connection, the artistic image should be considered not merely as the result of resemblance or skillful reproduction of the external appearance of an object, but as a phenomenon of the transformation of content. What is at stake is the transition from a real thing to a conditional but convincing image in terms of belief in the reality of the depicted. Such a formulation of the question requires the simultaneous involvement of two research perspectives - phenomenological and semiotic. The former makes it possible to describe how the image appears in consciousness as an intentional object. The latter makes it possible to trace how depiction functions as a sign that not only denotes but also presents, interprets, and replaces reality.

Problem Statement. The main problem of this article is to clarify the mechanism by which a real thing is transformed into an artistic image in realist painting. This concerns not merely the technical transfer of the external features of an object onto the surface of a painting, but a more complex process as a result of which a real object acquires the form of a conditional yet convincing presence in the consciousness of the recipient. In this sense, the question arises: what exactly makes a depiction an image? Why is a system of lines

and patches of color perceived not as a set of material elements but as a certain autonomous reality?

Within the framework of this problem, several more specific tasks must be solved. First, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "image" and "depiction," since their identification obscures the specificity of artistic perception. Second, the factors that ensure the semantic transformation of an object into an image must be identified. Third, it is important to determine the role of experience, belief, intention, presentation, and interpretation in the process of image formation. Fourth, it is necessary to establish the relationship between phenomenology and semiotics in explaining the artistic image. Finally, it is necessary to critically evaluate the conception according to which the image in realist painting is an autonomous reality of consciousness arising as a result of the correlation between experience and belief.

Analysis of the State of Scholarly Development of the Topic. The problematics of image, depiction, and artistic reality are interdisciplinary in nature and have been developed in various intellectual traditions. In phenomenology, the foundational works for this topic are those of Husserl, who analyzed the intentionality of consciousness, the mechanisms of the constitution of the object, and the difference between sensory givenness and the object of intention (Husserl, 2014). His ideas were important for the further understanding of artistic perception as a special mode of givenness.

Within phenomenological aesthetics, the problem of depiction and the work of art was developed by Ingarden, who investigated the multilayered structure of the work of art, in particular the relationship between the material layer of depiction and the layer of reconstructed "aspects" (Ingarden, 1989). This made it possible to describe the internal structure of the pictorial work, although the question of the image in a broader sense remained open.

A special contribution to the understanding of visual experience and the specificity of painting was made by Merleau-Ponty, who connected perception not with the passive registration of the world but with the bodily rooted experience of vision (Merleau-Ponty, 2012). His proposition that depiction imitates not merely the object but the way it appears in experience is fundamental for this topic.

In terms of the aesthetic analysis of the work of art, an important place belongs to the works of Losev, who investigated myth, artistic form, and the specificity of the semantic being of the image (Losev, 1994, 1995). His reflections provide grounds for interpreting the image as a special reality of belief. Also significant for the analysis of depiction as a cultural form is the contribution of Lehenkyi, who considered depiction in the context of compositional synthesis and the cultural study of the image (Lehenkyi, 1995).

In semiotics, the concept of Deely is of key importance for this topic. Building on the line of Peirce, Deely analyzed the nature of the sign, object, interpretation, and interpretant (Deely, 2005). His approach makes it possible to see that depiction functions not merely as a bearer of visual information, but as an element of a more complex semiotic process in which

meaning arises as a result of the triadic structure of signification.

Thus, the scholarly development of the topic demonstrates the presence of two powerful lines of analysis - phenomenological and semiotic. At the same time, what still requires further elaboration is precisely their combination in the study of realist painting, as well as clarification of how intentional givenness, sign structure, experience, belief, and aesthetic autonomy are combined in the pictorial image.

Research Methodology. The methodological basis of the article is the combination of phenomenological, hermeneutic, and semiotic approaches. The phenomenological method is applied to describe the image from the point of view of its immediate givenness to consciousness, the mode of its intentional constitution, and its lived experience. The hermeneutic approach makes it possible to trace how the meaning of the work is formed in interaction with interpretation. Semiotic analysis is used to clarify how depiction functions as a sign, what its structure is, and what role the interpretant plays in the formation of the image.

The study is theoretical and analytical in nature and is based on a comparative consideration of the concepts of Husserl, Ingarden, Merleau-Ponty, Losev, and Deely. In addition, the method of art-historical interpretation is used for the analysis of specific examples from painting.

Phenomenology and semiotics are often presented as alternative approaches: the former focuses on consciousness and lived experience, the latter on signs and structures of signification. However, in the case of realist painting, it is advisable to regard them not as mutually exclusive but as complementary methodologies.

Phenomenology makes it possible to clarify **how** the image is given to consciousness. It describes it as an intentional object constituted on the basis of sensory material, experience, attention, reduction, and vision. It explains the internal mechanism of the transition from the material plane to figurative presence.

Semiotics, in turn, makes it possible to clarify **through what** and **within what structure** this transition takes place. It shows that depiction functions as a sign-bearer, that its meaning is not immediate but arises in the process of interpretation, and that the interpretant plays a key role in this.

Thus, phenomenology describes the image from the side of its lived experience, whereas semiotics describes it from the side of its sign organization. Their combination makes it possible to see that the artistic image is both an intentional and a sign-based formation. It does not exist without consciousness, but neither is it reducible to subjective experience; it has a material basis, but is not exhausted by it; it functions as a sign, but is not equal to mere signification.

It is precisely in the process of such a synthesis that the most relevant theoretical model of the artistic image in realist painting appears possible.

The phenomenological approach of Husserl allows one to consider the image not as a thing that simply exists in the external world, but as the result of the intentional activity of consciousness (Husserl, 2014). For Husserl, sensory data never coincide with

the object itself. What we see is given to us in "adumbrations" - partial, changing, perspectively conditioned moments of perception. The object as a stable whole emerges only thanks to the synthesis performed by consciousness.

Applied to painting, this means that patches of color, contours, and textural relations are not the image itself. They perform a representational function and serve as sensory material on the basis of which consciousness constitutes an intentional object. The image does not simply "reside" in the depiction; it is formed as a result of consciousness being directed toward this sensory material. Thus, already at the level of Husserlian analysis, the fundamental difference between the material plane of the painting and the image as that which arises in experience becomes evident.

Phenomenological reduction acquires special significance here. When contemplating a painting, the recipient, on the one hand, does not cease to know that what stands before them is a surface covered with paint. On the other hand, this material factuality is reduced, pushed into the background. Consciousness, as it were, "brackets" the immediate material status of the depiction in order to open another level of givenness - the figurative one. Reduction becomes the means that allows the plane to be transformed into the space of the image.

However, in Husserl the question remains insufficiently clarified as to why consciousness agrees to see in a material depiction the image of a real thing. His conception convincingly describes the mechanism of intentionality, but explains less distinctly the motivational moment of the transition from perceiving the means of depiction to accepting figurative reality. It is precisely this lacuna that makes an appeal to other concepts necessary.

Ingarden develops phenomenological analysis toward a special investigation of the work of art (Ingarden, 1989). In his view, the painting has a multi-layered structure. Its first layer is formed by the material means of depiction - paints, lines, textures, and visually fixed elements. The second layer consists of the "aspects" of things reconstructed in these elements.

This distinction is methodologically important because it makes it possible to see clearly that in painting two realities always coexist: the material and the intentional. Ingarden shows that the aspect is not identical with the physical depiction, but arises as a result of its perception. In this sense, the "aspect" may be interpreted as the phenomenological correlate of reproduced visual experience.

At the same time, the concept of "aspect" does not fully encompass what is meant by image. An aspect is first of all a mode of the visual appearance of a thing, its perceived side. The image includes more: not only appearance, but also semantic intention, emotional orientation, and aesthetic organization. That is why, although Ingarden's approach is extremely useful for the analysis of the structure of the painting, it cannot exhaustively explain the artistic self-sufficiency of the image.

From this perspective, the image is broader than the reconstructed "aspect." It not only reproduces the

experience of seeing, but also endows it with a new status - the status of aesthetically significant reality.

In the conception of Merleau-Ponty, the problem of the pictorial image is transferred to the plane of bodily rooted perception (Merleau-Ponty, 2012). Unlike a purely representational understanding of depiction, Merleau-Ponty shows that perception is an active, bodily, and ontologically rooted process. A thing is not simply given to us; it opens itself within a field of vision structured by the body, movement, habit, and the horizon of experience.

In this context, the idea that depiction imitates not so much the object itself as **visual experience** is especially important. That is why several conventional strokes can evoke the impression of a face, and relations of shadow and light the impression of volume. The realism of a painting lies not in the literal duplication of a thing, but in the reproduction of the conditions of its recognition.

Merleau-Ponty also helps one look differently at the problem of belief. If the image becomes convincing for consciousness, this happens because consciousness recognizes in it the structure of already assimilated experience. But this recognition is not automatic: it requires a certain act of belief in the depiction. Experience forms the horizon of the possible, and belief performs the act of acceptance. It is precisely at this point that Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology begins to intersect with the line developed in the author's text.

Also important is Merleau-Ponty's assertion that in "normal perception" the content of what is perceived appears as instituted in the thing itself, rather than as arbitrarily constructed by the subject (Merleau-Ponty, 2012, p. 339). This means that in the experience of a painting, consciousness does not simply impose meaning on the material surface, but responds to a certain semantic proposal embedded in the mode of depiction. Thus, the image arises as a meeting of experience and intention.

Losev's philosophy of the image makes it possible to move from the analysis of perception to the analysis of the semantic self-sufficiency of the image (Losev, 1994, 1995). For Losev, myth is not simply fiction, but a real form of consciousness for the one who lives within it. This thesis has a direct bearing on art, since the artistic image likewise functions as a reality of belief.

When Losev speaks of the image, he in effect shows that meaning is not exhausted by external visibility. External appearance can substitute for another, deeper reality, and act on its behalf. This is especially important for painting: depiction not only presents an object, but becomes its image, that is, its semantic representative endowed with its own power of presence.

No less significant is Losev's conception of artistic form (Losev, 1995). In the philosopher's reflections, artistic form is dual: it always contains both **what** is manifested and **how** it is manifested. It is precisely this "duality" that creates artistry as a special form of adequacy between content and the mode of its expression. Thus, the artistic image is not merely a sign of an object; it is the realization of a certain idea of vision, a certain idea of expression.

From this follows an important conclusion: the artistic self-sufficiency of the image lies not in a break with the object, but in the fact that the object is given in it already in a transformed, semantically intensified form. That is why aesthetic interest is concentrated not on the thing itself, but on the image of the thing, on the way in which it appears before consciousness.

Deely's conception is key to the semiotic understanding of depiction (Deely, 2005). Unlike binary models of the sign, Deely emphasizes that semiosis always has a triadic structure: sign, object signified, and interpretant. Thanks to this, the sign does not merely point to an object, but enters into complex relations with consciousness, experience, and meaning.

For the analysis of painting, the concept of the **sign-vehicle** is particularly important. Depiction functions as a vehicle of experience: it objectifies visual experience and makes it available to consciousness. But in itself it is not yet an artistic image. It merely creates a pattern, a schema, that requires interpretation.

In this context, the interpretant is what transforms the sign structure into a meaningful situation. It is not simply a commentary or external explanation, but a conditional though factual-for-consciousness picture of what follows from the relation between sign and signified. In the case of painting, the interpretant may be understood as the situation of seeing in which the depicted is perceived as present.

Especially valuable in Deely is the understanding that the sign does not merely replace the object, but appears as an independent object that "stands for something other than itself" (Deely, 2005). This means that in painting what matters is not only what is depicted, but also how exactly the sign realizes its substitution. Here semiotics comes directly close to the problem of artistic form.

The interpretant also turns out to be the meeting place of experience and belief. Presentation appeals to experience because it is oriented toward recognition. But at the same time it requires belief, since the depicted object is not directly present. In this sense, the interpretant is the factual situation in which consciousness accepts the conditional reality of the image.

Presentation of the Main Material. If we take the methodological principles described above as our basis, it can be said that belief, on the one hand, and experience, on the other, are two intentions, one of which is directed by consciousness toward reality, while the other is, conversely, a projection of reality onto consciousness. In this sense, the image does not imitate real actuality, but becomes "personal being" (Losev, 1994, p. 73); on the basis of the givenness represented by depiction, it creates its own self-sufficient consciousness. "Its own" in the sense that this consciousness expresses and concerns only that which is given in the concrete image. In this sense, a still life with fruit on a tablecloth, Mont Sainte-Victoire, a face from a Fayum portrait, warriors on a Greek relief or on a Scythian pectoral - all these are realities which, from the moment of their creation, live their own self-sufficient life nourished only by experience and belief. Thus, the reality of images becomes self-sufficient; it replaces the perception of the real thing. In this connection, one may say that the image becomes those "eyes"

through which we look at reality, that is, an analogue of perception in Merleau-Ponty's sense or an "iconic equivalent of perception" in Eco's sense. In this regard, the phenomenon of seeing acquires the significance of a key factor; it consists in the concretization of the motive, that is, the desire to see in what is depicted the image of this or that object. This means the comprehension of a particular configuration of spots and lines on a plane as the depicted object given through the mediation of these spots and lines. What is lacking in the scheme described is only one link - the mediator, the means by which the very process of correlation, that is, the "meeting" of experience and belief, takes place.

Experience requires objectification, that is, awareness, and therefore there arises a need for a carrier through which experience is transmitted and fixed, since only in this case can it be applied by consciousness. According to Deely (2005), a thing not reduced to experience exists separately from human thought - physically or really. By contrast, a thing already tested in experience and thereby made conscious becomes an object. Thus, an object is a thing that exists in experience, or more precisely, "acquires existence according to experience." The fixing means here is the sign as a "pattern" "according to which things and objects interweave to form the fabric of experience" (Deely, 2005, p. 109). Therefore, it is precisely the sign that objectifies experience, expressing it and making it "available through some sensory modality" for understanding (Deely, 2005, p. 110). In our case, such a "sensory modality" is depiction, which objectifies visual experience by representing it through the "aspect" of the depicted thing.

If the artist has at their disposal the means of depiction on the one hand and the object of depiction on the other, then at the basis of depiction there will always be an idea - an understanding of **how** to apply, group, distribute, combine, juxtapose, and so on, these means in such a way as to convey through them the idea of the depicted object as adequately as necessary for it to persuade and induce belief in the depicted object. But at the same time, it is also the idea of expression itself, which induces belief not in the actual object, whose existence, as shown above, is "put in quotation marks," reduced, but in the depicted object, and in the object depicted **precisely in this way**. Perhaps the best illustration of this is Cezanne's series of views of Mont Sainte-Victoire. In this case, we have the same prototype - the mountain landscape and the field before it, depicted from an analogous or even identical angle. Only the images in which this landscape appears differ. What does the evolution of these images consist in, if not in the evolution of the very idea of expression? If this is so, then the question arises: what does such an idea persuade us of? And what is its aim? In any case, the verisimilitude of depiction is not the aim here. The idea represents not the mountain and its surroundings, but the very mode of depiction or **seeing**; it emphasizes not the actual reality of the landscape, but seeks to persuade us of the reality of the landscape depicted **in just this way**. That there exists a real object - Mont Sainte-Victoire - is also clear from the depiction, but this reality, or rather its idea, is not dominant. What interests

the artist is not the appearance of the mountain in actuality, but its image, **vision realized in a certain idea** of the construction of the depiction. It is precisely as a consequence of such a duality of ideas and their correlation that the self-sufficiency of the artistic image arises. This self-sufficiency consists in the fact that the object of belief becomes not so much the depicted object itself, not so much its own verisimilitude, as its understanding - the image - and therefore the idea of its expression, the compositional idea through which this image is formed. The value emphasis of form, taken specifically as "artistic," is thus shifted from objective givenness to its interpretation.

It must be especially emphasized that the sign does not simply replace the object signified, but is taken as an independent object, fundamentally different from that which it signifies. The sign is an object. It does not simply "stand for another," but "stands for something other than itself," as Deely (2005) emphasizes. In that case, the interpretant becomes that "marker" from which it becomes clear **how** the sign enters into relations with "something other" - with the signified. Thus, what is at issue is that the interpretant reflects the mode of signification, and more specifically, the mode of expression, since the sign, in the case of depiction, not only replaces but expresses the signified.

In light of the above, the relation between the idea and the interpretant also becomes clear. The objecthood of the sign, its difference from the signified, determines the mode of expression carried out by the sign as the representation or presentation of the signified before human consciousness. Consciousness has no access to the signified object itself; it has access only to the sign that presents this object, standing in for it and replacing it. One may say that the sign reveals the substituted object by presenting it, in the case of depiction by showing its appearance. Presentation is nothing other than the transmission of content into consciousness, its representation in a certain appearance or form. It is evident that this appearance or form is presentation itself, since it is only in it that content resides and is expressed; therefore, the understanding of content is determined solely by its presentation, or more precisely, by the mode of its realization.

Thus, depiction as an "aspect" in Ingarden's terminology, presented by the sign, becomes for consciousness that object in reaction to which, according to Santayana (2014), "belief is imperceptibly imposed upon the organism." The presentation of the "aspect," or more precisely the idea of this presentation, is what induces belief in the object signified by the sign but not directly present. Consciousness is simply left with no alternative but to accept on faith what is presented, relying on previously acquired experience and guided by the idea of presentation itself.

The above reflections may be reduced to the following. Presentation as a mode of expressing content is the idea in which lies the inducement to believe in the object signified by the sign. The interpretant, accordingly, is that from which consciousness learns, and on the basis of which it judges, the signified object - the appearance in which the latter appears before consciousness.

From what has been said, an important conclusion may be drawn regarding the interpretant: its indifference with respect to actuality. The interpretant is a factual situation that is not determined by actuality, although it may correspond to it or not, but is accepted on faith. Recalling Losev's reflections, one may say that the interpretant is a myth through which consciousness makes sense of a particular phenomenon of actuality and which accordingly replaces that actuality, that is, itself becomes for consciousness the reality with which it connects and within which it thinks its own existence (Losev, 1994).

Thus, the two pairs of binary relations discussed above - "sign-signified" and "sign-human being" - are transformed, with the introduction of the interpretant, into a ternary relation: sign-interpretant-signified. As can be seen, the sign performs in these relations the function of mediator between two spheres - human consciousness and actuality. The interpretant, in turn, performs the function of a referent that speaks both on behalf of consciousness and on behalf of actuality, namely: it allows consciousness to make sense of actuality through a factual situation into which it is introduced, and it allows actuality to be reflected in consciousness through presentation, in the realization of which the factual situation consists. This is the basis for the following conclusion. The situation created by the interpretant is realized in the first case as belief, because the interpretant is a situation accepted on faith, and in the second as experience, since presentation appeals to experience and is designed for the recognition in the "aspect" presented by the sign of the signified object. Therefore, it may be said that the interpretant becomes the situation in which belief and experience are correlated. In accordance with the above, the mode by which these two factors correlate is presentation.

Conclusions

Summarizing the course of the above reflections, it may be said that the mode of correlating experience and belief is the creation of a factual situation in which consciousness, through presentation, realizes vision as an idea, and therefore as belief, since belief is an idea in intention, while by means of the sign the experience of seeing, that is, visual experience, is realized. The factual situation in question is the situation of interpretation, which realizes itself as presentation. This coincides with the resolution of the antinomy of the two types of sign relation: sign-signified and sign-consciousness, the medium of whose synthesis becomes the interpretant. The latter thereby combines two qualities: it appears as consciousness, in which the signified is reflected, and at the same time as actuality, that is, a conditional yet real-for-consciousness "picture" in which this actuality appears before it. One may say that consciousness thus **transforms actuality**, that is, modifies it, adapting it to its own needs. Yet actuality also moves toward consciousness, convincing it of the reality of what has been seen, appealing to previously acquired experience and calling upon it to rely on that experience. Of course, this may be assumed only if one remembers that what is at issue is a conditional situation in which actuality is represented, and therefore replaced, by the sign - the depiction - which is taken for

actuality, while the reality of what is depicted is subject to phenomenological reduction.

References

1. Deely, J. (2005). *Basics of semiotics* (4th ed.). Tartu University Press.
2. Husserl, E. (2014). *Ideas for a pure phenomenology and phenomenological philosophy: First book: A general introduction to pure phenomenology* (D. O. Dahlstrom, Trans.). Hackett Publishing.
3. Ingarden, R. (1989). *Ontology of the work of art: The musical work, the picture, the architectural work, the film* (R. Meyer & J. T. Goldthwait, Trans.). Ohio University Press.
4. Lehenkyi, Y. H. (1995). *Kul'turologiya izobrazheniya. Opyt kompozitsionnogo sinteza* [Culturology of depiction: An experience of compositional synthesis]. HALPU.
5. Losev, A. F. (1994). Dialektika mifa [Dialectics of myth]. In *Mif - Chislo - Sushchnost'* [Myth - Number - Essence]. Mysl.
6. Losev, A. F. (1995). Dialektika khudozhestvennoy formy [Dialectics of artistic form]. In *Forma - Stil' - Vyrazhenie* [Form - Style - Expression]. Mysl.
7. Merleau-Ponty, M. (2012). *Phenomenology of perception* (D. A. Landes, Trans.). Routledge.
8. Santayana, G. (2014). *Scepticism and animal faith: Introduction to a system of philosophy*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.